

Can Voltage Pulses Be Used for VT Frequency Characterization?

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Abstract— The frequency characterization of instrument transformers is a topic of ongoing discussion, and the identification of a standardized methodology to perform it is still an open issue. Among the possible approaches discussed in international standards and literature, the use of pulse signals is particularly attractive due to the rapidity of execution and their compatibility with existing standard tests already performed on voltage transformers. In this context, this paper investigates the pros and the issue of using impulsive voltages as test waveforms for the MV voltage transformers wideband characterization. The study is conducted from both the theoretical and experimental point of view by performing preliminary tests on two commercial sensors.

Keywords— instrument transformers, voltage pulse, impulsive waveforms, high frequency, frequency characterization.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the great advances in the performance of switching semiconductor devices have led to an increasing use of switching power converters in power systems. In turns, their performances have increased in terms of efficiency, voltage and current levels and switching frequency. The result is that also Medium Voltage (MV) grids, as Low Voltage (LV) grids, are experiencing increased conducted electromagnetic disturbances at increased frequency [1], [2].

From the point of view of Distribution System Operators (DSOs) it is very important to guarantee the quality of the distributed voltage. This gives stronger and stronger importance to Power Quality (PQ) measurements also in MV grids, up to hundreds of kilohertz [3], [4].

It is known that voltage and current measurements at MV level need Instrument Transformers (ITs), namely Voltage and Current Transformers (VTs and CTs), to adapt their amplitude to the input range of PQ measuring instruments.

From a standard point of view, ITs are covered by the International Electrotechnical Commission (IEC) 61869 standard family. In particular, the second edition of IEC 61869-1 (2024) [5] now extends accuracy requirements to frequencies up to 150 kHz and even 500 kHz. However, these standards do not provide guidance on measurement methodologies, generators architectures, test procedures, reference instrumentation, nor uncertainty evaluation for frequencies beyond the power frequency range.

For what concerns the measurement of the frequency behavior of ITs, the technical report IEC 61869-103 [6] states that it can be measured using various test waveforms: harmonics superposition to the fundamental frequency or impulses.

From a literature point of view, a quite wide number of papers deal with the measurement of the frequency behaviour of VTs and CTs beyond the power frequency. In general, it is well recognized within the scientific community that assessment of the frequency behaviour of ITs requires test signals consisting of a fundamental component (either Direct Current, DC, or Alternating Current, AC, 50/60 Hz), combined with additional spectral components with lower amplitude [7]-[9]. The main disadvantage of this approach is essentially linked to the complexity and the cost of the necessary test instrumentation. This is the reason why some papers deal with simplified methods for the frequency characterization of ITs, both VTs as well as CTs [10]-[14].

Another approach for the frequency characterization of ITs is based on the use of pulses as test waveforms [15], [16]. Pulses are a kind of transient waveform with a very wide spectrum: this represents a great potential advantage, in terms of test duration, since, within one single test, ITs could be tested across a wide frequency range. Even if, to the best of the authors' knowledge, a very few papers deal about this topic, the possibility of using pulses for IT characterization is

an idea very diffused in the standardization committees, as [6] demonstrates.

The activity here presented is developed according to the framework of the European Partnership in Metrology (EPM) 22NRM06 “ADMIT” [17] which aims to establish suitable parameters for the definition of the accuracy of ITs, and the related measurement instrumentation, in the frequency range up to 150 kHz. Within the activities that will be carried out during the project there is also the development of simplified methods for frequency characterization of ITs.

Therefore, in this paper, the use of voltage pulses for the measurement of the frequency behavior of VTs is analyzed.

The structure of the paper is as follows. Section II provides a brief literature review and Section III describes the implementation of the proposed setup. Section IV and V deal with some preliminary results coming from theoretical analysis and experimental activity. Finally, Section VI draws the conclusions.

II. VT FREQUENCY CHARACTERIZATION: LITERATURE AND STANDARD APPROACHES

The characterisation methods, test waveforms and measurement setups for the verification of the metrological performance of MV ITs up to 9 kHz are studied in many papers, such as [7]-[14] and [18]-[33]; some of these papers are coauthored by some authors of the present paper. In the literature, it is quite widely recognised that the measurement of the frequency behaviour of the ITs, especially the inductive ones, should be performed by applying waveforms composed of a fundamental tone (DC or AC 50/60 Hz) and one or more spectral tones with reduced amplitude. These kinds of tests are generally referred to as FH1 (Fundamental plus 1 Harmonic) and FHN (Fundamental plus N Harmonic components) and these represent, of course, a simplified version of realistic power grid scenarios; however, they always include the MV tone at the rated frequency, which will certainly be present under real operating conditions.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, in scientific literature the investigated frequency range has been confined to 10 kHz, with only a few papers that investigate beyond this frequency. However, those that explored higher frequencies remain restricted to a quite low-frequency range, e.g., 20 kHz, as in [31].

As already said in Section I, FH1 and FHN tests typically require complex and costly instrumentation and so not all the calibration laboratories are able to perform them. This is the reason why the topic of simplified methods for the frequency characterization of ITs is quite diffused in literature [10]-[14].

In particular, one of the most diffused simplified method is the use of Sinusoidal Frequency Sweep (SFS), basing on the use of low voltage (typically up to tens of volt) sine waves with variable frequency. It has the great advantage of the use of low cost instrumentation, diffused in practically every measurement laboratory. However, [13] and [30], demonstrates that it outputs a frequency behavior quite different from that obtained with FH1 or FHN tests, since the low voltage amplitude is not able to accurately stimulate all the non-linearities of the IT (f.i. the magnetic core saturation or the hysteresis).

Another paper that goes in the direction of simplifying the necessary instrumentation is [14]. It proposes the use of test

waveforms composed by a fundamental component, with the rated amplitude and frequency, and a small damped sine wave, namely a Damped Oscillatory Wave (DOW). This kind of waveform has the advantage of having a quite wide spectrum, allowing for the IT frequency characterization within a single test, with stronger reduction of test duration.

Another approach proposed in literature, is based on the use of voltage pulses [15] as test waveforms. Like a DOW, a pulse has a wide frequency spectrum, potentially allowing for a faster frequency characterization of ITs.

With respect to the DOWS, the pulses have other two potential advantages. They come from the fact that impulse test is a kind of test standardized by [34]. This means that calibration laboratories equipped with the necessary instruments and standardized procedures already exist. The second advantage comes from the fact that according to [5], ITs must be subjected to pulse test before they can be put on the market. Combining these two potential advantages with the possibility to perform a frequency characterization in a faster way than with FH1 or FHN tests make the use of pulses very attractive. In other words, considering that the impulse test must already be performed on ITs and that, therefore, testing laboratories are equipped with the necessary experimental setups, it could be possible, with minor modifications, to also extract information about the frequency response during the procedure for the insulation verification.

III. LIGHTNING IMPULSE: EXPERIMENTAL SETUP DESCRIPTION

Considering the definition given in [34], a lightning impulse (LI) is a voltage impulse with a front time shorter than 20 μ s. LIs are test waveforms used to evaluate the dielectric stress caused by transient overvoltages due to lightning strikes or disruptive discharges, in order to validate electrical components or devices.

The Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica (INRiM), through its High Voltage and High Power Laboratory (LATFC), is equipped with the instrumentation required to calibrate LI waveforms up to 600 kV.

For the experimental activity described in this paper, a Passoni Villa GTP 32 generator was used. It generates impulses up to 32 kV with an energy of 358 J. The generator is built according to the scheme of a single-stage Marx generator that includes a voltage step-up stage with transformer, a diode bridge rectifier, a spark gap, resistors, and capacitors. Various internal resistors can be properly configured in order to control the impulse properties. The internal capacitance is used to store energy, which is then transferred to the dielectric of the test object. The generator can produce both positive and negative impulses.

To measure the generated pulse, a device from LATFC, called IMP6, was used. It is a resistive divider capable to measure LI up to 17 kV while it can measure up to 28 kV when combined with an attenuator. The calibration of the measuring system for the impulse is done by comparison with a reference measuring system according to IEC 60060-2 standard. The expanded uncertainty of the divider was evaluated for different configurations. For the standard IMP6, the uncertainty is 3.0 % for the scale factor (SF), 3.5 % for both time constants T1 and T2. When an attenuator was added to the IMP6 configuration, the uncertainty for the scale factor slightly decreased to 2.6 %, while the uncertainties for T1 and T2 increased marginally to 3.7 % and 3.6 %, respectively.

Table I summarizes the main characteristics of Passoni Villa GTP 32 generator and IMP6

TABLE I: CHARACTERISTICS OF LIGHTNING IMPULSE SYSTEM

Name	Type	Voltage	Scale factor
Passoni Villa GTP 32	Generator	Up to 32 kV	-
IMP6	Resistive voltage divider	Up to 17 kV	270 V/V
IMP6 plus attenuator	Resistive voltage divider	Up to 28 kV	400 V/V

The output voltage of the reference device is acquired using a Tektronix TDS 3012C digital oscilloscope, featuring two channels, a 100 MHz bandwidth, and a sampling rate of 1.25 GHz.

IV. ANALYSIS OF FREQUENCY CHARACTERISTICS OF PULSE WAVEFORMS

The mathematical expression of the voltage pulse for the tests described in Section III is given by the following equation (1) and it is taken from international standard EN 60060-1 [34].

$$v_{\text{pulse}}(t) = V \left(e^{-\frac{(t-t_d)}{\tau_1}} - e^{-\frac{(t-t_d)}{\tau_2}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where the parameter values are those of the 1.2/50 lightning pulse [34]. The purpose of this Section is to highlight and discuss the critical issues associated to the frequency domain analysis of signal (1), used for the characterization of ITs, compared to the analysis of the periodic multitone waveforms such as FH1 and FHN commonly used in the ITs test approaches presented in the literature and discussed in Section II.

First of all, the signal (1) is non-periodic but the Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) implicitly assumes periodicity, effectively creating a periodic extension of the signal. The signal drops to approximately 0.01% of the peak voltage within 0.65 ms, so the time window should not be shorter than this duration in order to avoid discontinuities in the periodicized signal resulting from the DFT. On the other hand, to achieve a sufficient spectral resolution to observe the 50 Hz component, a time window of at least 20 ms is required. Considering the real case, the pulse generation is typically carried out manually and between two tests it is necessary to wait for the relays resetting, it is reasonable to assume that only a single pulse will occur within a 20 ms interval. Consequently, the signal will remain at zero for the majority of the 20 ms observation time window.

Based on these considerations, a numerical simulation is carried out to assess the conditions under which the IT is tested, with particular focus on the characteristics of the input excitation spectrum. The signal (1) is numerically simulated and the parameters t_d , τ_1 and τ_2 are identified in order to properly fit the actual 1.2/50 lightning pulse generated and measured using the instrumentation described in Section III. The resulting simulated pulse is a single unit-amplitude impulse within a 20 ms window. A DFT of the signal is computed and the resulting amplitude spectrum is observed. It shows that the maximum amplitude of 0.52 % of the pulse peak value is associated to the DC component whereas at 50 Hz, the amplitude is slightly lower (0.51 %). It gradually decreases to 0.4 % at 2 kHz and drops below 0.1 % beyond

11.6 kHz. At 150 kHz, the amplitude is further reduced to $\sim 50 \mu\text{V/V}$. As a preliminary comment from this analysis, it is evidenced the importance to distinguish between the impulse peak value and the amplitude at the power frequency, as only a small portion of the signal energy is associated with that frequency. Moreover, the dominant spectral component occurs at DC, which presents a significant issue when characterizing inductive ITs, as the presence of a DC component can lead to magnetic core saturation. Considering frequencies other than DC or the power frequency, it is observed that the first harmonics of the power frequency have amplitudes of the same order of magnitude of the DC and power frequency components, within a few parts per thousand (f.i. 0.47 % at 1 kHz). This spectral amplitude structure is rather unrealistic, as ITs are typically used in power grid scenarios where harmonic amplitudes represent only a small percentage of the fundamental frequency at 50/60 Hz component. As the higher-frequency components, they exhibit significantly low amplitudes, meaning that the characterization of the IT in this frequency range occurs with a very small signal-to-noise ratio.

An additional analysis is conducted on a simulated signal over a reduced time window of 1 ms, corresponding to a spectral resolution of 1 kHz, in order to evaluate the influence this digital signal processing parameter on the resulting spectral characteristics. In this case, the issue of magnetic core saturation in inductive ITs becomes more pronounced but, on the other hand, the amplitude of the high frequency components increases, enabling characterization under better signal to noise ratio conditions. Specifically, the maximum amplitude is at DC component where it reaches 10.4 % of the pulse peak amplitude whereas at 1 kHz it is 9.6 %, and it gradually decreases to approximately 0.1% at 150 kHz.

To summarize, this first simple analysis of the spectral content of the simulated signal (1) conducted using both 20 ms and 1 ms time windows, has revealed several issues in its application for characterizing ITs. Specifically, the most critical issues are related to 1) the presence of a high DC component which can be highly undesired when inductive ITs are considered; 2) the 50 Hz tone does not assume the rated IT amplitude but only a very small percentage of it; 3) the high-frequency tones have very low amplitudes.

In addition to the issues identified with the analysis of the theoretical signal, further complexities arise when considering a real pulse signal. For example, Fig. 1 shows the rising edge of an actual impulse acquired in the laboratory, and it can be observed that very high frequency oscillations, in the order of megahertz, occur along the rising edge.

V. EXPERIMENTAL TESTS AND THEORETICAL ANALYSIS OF POSSIBLE ISSUES IN IT CHARACTERIZATION WITH PULSES

A. Experimental tests

This section presents the first analysis of experimental tests conducted on two commercial MV sensors, using the experimental setup described in Section III. The only difference with the setup and procedure presented in Section III lies in the use of an additional acquisition channel for the acquisition of the output voltages of the sensors. The main features of the two voltage sensors are summarized in Table II.

TABLE II: MAIN FEATURES OF THE TWO INVESTIGATED MV VOLTAGE TRANSDUCER

Name	Type	Rated primary voltage (kV)	Rated Scale Factor (V/V)	Accuracy class
RVD	Resistive Voltage divider	20/√3	10000	0.5
VT	Inductive	22/√3	220	0.5

As a first step, the RVD has been supplied with pulses with increasing amplitude of the voltage peak. It was immediately observed that the RVD does not attenuate the input signal by the rated SF, but, instead, it attenuated the peak by a SF of more than one order of magnitude smaller. This behavior is due to the spectral content of the pulse and the frequency response of the RVD, in fact at high frequencies, parasitic capacitances and become crucial resulting in a new value for SF, which is inherently unpredictable. In fact, it is important to note that the frequency response of the RVD is not known in advance, since its determination is exactly the aim of this characterization approach. The lack of prior knowledge of the frequency response, and therefore of the expected amplitude of the output signal, poses a critical issue, as it becomes difficult to properly configure and size the acquisition system in advance. In this respect, a real example is provided in Fig. 2 that shows the output voltage of the RVD when it is supplied with a pulse with a peak value of 1.5 kV. As it can be observed, the measured peak clearly exceeds 10 V, implying a scale factor of less than 150 V/V. The acquisition system was set up according to the nominal values in Table II. However, as shown in Fig. 2b, the input channel is saturated, even though the applied voltage is well below the RVD's rated primary voltage and the expected output was 0.15 V. In particular, the saturation of the acquisition system channel is due to high-amplitude, high-frequency oscillations (in the order of megahertz), triggered by the excitation of such

Fig. 2. (a) Voltage at the output of the VD when it supplied with a pulse with a peak value of 1.5 kV. (b) a zoom highlighting the high amplitude and high frequency oscillations due to the VD high frequency response.

frequency components by the real input pulse (see Fig. 1). In this range, the RVD exhibits poles and zeros that give rise to resonance phenomena. The link between the poles and zeros of the DUT transfer function and their response to pulse is described and discussed in depth in the following Section V.B, with specific reference to tests performed on the inductive VT.

B. Theoretical Analysis of possible issues in IT characterization with pulses

The analysis is carried out in two steps. The first step involves analytically describing the complex frequency behaviour of the transfer function of a VT, measured at low voltage over the 100 Hz to 150 kHz range. The transfer function was obtained by applying a 7 V single-tone frequency sweep and calculating the complex ratio between the VT output signal and the input signal. The transfer function of the VT, as the ratio of the output response to the input stimulus, has a zero at the origin ($z_0 = 0$ rad/s) which reflects the VT's inability to transfer a DC stimulus. The system includes two poles: one at a very low frequency, marking the onset of VT operation, and another at a high frequency, representing the limit imposed by the acquisition system. Additionally, there exists a sequence of complex-conjugate zero-pole pairs characterized by their natural frequencies ω_{nz} and ω_{np} and by the damping coefficients ζ_{zi} for the zeros and ζ_{pi} for the poles. The structure of the VT transfer function, in Laplace domain, is provided in the (2).

$$G(s) = \rho \frac{s}{(s + p_0)(s + p_1)} \frac{\prod_i (s^2 + 2\zeta_{zi}\omega_{nzi}s + \omega_{nzi}^2)}{\prod_i (s^2 + 2\zeta_{pi}\omega_{npi}s + \omega_{npi}^2)} \quad (2)$$

Across the entire bandwidth, a regular pattern of zero-pole pairs has been observed. To simplify parameter identification, the natural frequency of each complex pole is described using:

$$\omega_{npi} = \omega_{nzi} + \Delta\omega_i \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta\omega_i$ represents the frequency separation between the zero and its corresponding pole.

With the VT transfer function architecture thus defined, an optimization algorithm can be used to identify its parameters by minimizing the deviation between simulation results and experimental measurements which shows the excellent agreement between the measured and simulated VT gain—both in magnitude and phase—up to 150 kHz.

Fig. 3. Comparison between the measured and computed complex gain of the inductive VT.

The identification of the VT transfer function enables the second step, which is the computation of the VT output when the input is stimulated with a pulse signal. Using standard simulation tools available in Python or MATLAB, it is then possible to compute the system's response (described by $G(s)$)

to an input stimulus such as the atmospheric pulse used in testing. Fig. 4 presents a comparison between the measured and simulated time-domain responses. The computed behavior reproduces the low frequency oscillation in a satisfactory way. However, the high frequency oscillations are not reproduced because they exceed 150 kHz, the bandwidth limit of the low-voltage frequency sweep.

Fig.4 1. Comparison between the measured and computed inductive VT response the pulse voltage.

C. Summary of the main findings

Considering the findings from the previous sections, this section presents Table III highlighting the pros and cons of using the pulse signal for the frequency characterization of ITs, compared to more established waveform types found in the literature.

TABLE III: PROS AND CONS IN USING THE PULSE FOR THE VT CHARACTERIZATION VS FHI/FHN AND LV SFS

	<i>Experiment at setup</i>	<i>DSP</i>	<i>Speed</i>	<i>Realistic signal similarity</i>
PULSE	pros in the generation but difficulty in safely sizing the acquisition systems	cons	pros	cons
FHI/FHN	cons	pros	cons	pros
LV SFS	Pros	pros	cons	cons

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper has investigated the potential of using pulse waveforms for the VTs frequency characterization. Both simulation and experimental analyses have revealed several issues. Since the pulse waveform is inherently non-periodic, its analysis in the frequency domain is not straightforward compared to the analysis under FHI and FHN test waveforms.

The choice of the time window for the analysis plays a crucial role, as it directly influences the spectral content being analyzed. Additionally, the DC component of the impulse may cause saturation of inductive VTs iron core, compromising the validity of the measurement results. Moreover, it must be considered that the peak value of the pulse does not correspond to the amplitude of the tone at rated operating

frequency, meaning that the VTs are not supplied in a way that replicates real-world conditions (high amplitude component at rated frequency and superimposed low amplitude tones).

The frequency response of the DUT, unknown before the test, since the test is meant to determine it, greatly affects the amplitude and shape of its output voltage when a pulse is applied. More in detail, the paper has demonstrated, both experimentally and theoretically, that high-frequency poles and zeros in the VTs transfer function can lead to amplified output signals, often exceeding expectations based on nominal SFS. In some cases, these unexpected oscillations can saturate and damage the acquisition system used during standard impulse testing.

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